

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL BACKGROUND IN UTKIR HOSHIMOV'S AND JOHN STEINBECK'S NOVELS

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Abstract. *This thesis analyzes the social and historical background of great Uzbek writer Utkir Hoshimov and American novelist John Steinbeck, their most influential novels and socio-historical issues that influenced in creating their literary works. Both writers played significant role in shaping national identity. John Steinbeck mainly focused on human struggles during Great Depression period in America, in contrast, Utkir Hoshimov highlighted social dilemmas of ordinary people during World War II and post-independence period, deeply diving into humans' inner feelings and thoughts.*

Key words: *Utkir Hoshimov, John Steinbeck, social issues, Great Depression, historical background, post-independence, Uzbek literature, economic inequality, exploitation, migration, injustice.*

Introduction. Literature as a reflection of any nation often shows the social environment of the period in what it was written. Through literary works we can determine not only the main events happened in exact period but their influence on society and people who lived in that historical era. Society and human life are a fundamental source for author that inspires him to create masterpieces which can touch the deepest strings of human soul. John Steinbeck became the voice of American working class, illustrating major economic downturn (1929-late 1930s) which led to poverty, unemployment, homelessness and collapse in economy of the country. In his novel "Grapes of wrath" he portrayed economic inequality and exploitation, migration and injustice, showing ordinary people's willpower in overwhelming challenges of the harsh period.

The most significant Uzbek writer of modern literature Utkir Hoshimov emerged in the second half of the XX century, considered as the social, economic and political transformation period in Uzbekistan. He used his writings to portray moral and spiritual life of people in Soviet Uzbekistan mostly highlighting human value in his novels. His highly regarded work "Between two doors" describes deep psychological insight of nation which came across severe war, societal pressure and moral dilemmas between traditions and changing values of that time. This thesis explores the influence of social environment in John Steinbeck's "Grapes of wrath" and Utkir Hoshimov's "Between two doors" to appreciate the authenticity and depth of their literary works.

The effect of Great Depression to John Steinbeck's novel "Grapes of wrath". John Steinbeck was born in 1902 in California's Salinas valley, a small agricultural town. Later Steinbeck illustrates hardworking people of Salinas valley in his novels. Growing up in the family of county treasurer and schoolteacher provided stable educational base for future writer, shaping his empathy for the ordinary people. As a young man he worked in several manual labor jobs and during those years he came across with hard life of migrant workers. After World War I American economy flourished and these years considered as "Roaring twenties" in American history.

But later the country faced with tragic period known as Great Depression and it was the worst period in American history. One of the greatest works of novelist “Grapes of wrath” appeared in this harsh period describing people who were suffering from homelessness, anxiety and poverty. This novel characterizes American life in Depression time, criticizes capitalism, explains the difficulties people faced due to social issues and unity of working class in response to injustice.

The Grapes of Wrath is about poor tenant farmers from Oklahoma, who migrated to California and instead of prosperity find exploitation and poverty. Poor community united against the government and fought for dignity and solidarity. Steinbeck also criticizes the capitalistic system and economic failure of the country in Great depression. For this novel John Steinbeck became a Noble laureate. Working class even considered him as a spokesman of poor people, ordinary farmers. This novel not only read for pleasure but portrays the real historical event of the concrete period. The writing style of author, often regarded as a documentary, which reflects the real issues and conditions of his society.

Utkir Hoshimov was born in 1941, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Unlike Steinbeck's structured youth, Hoshimov involved to work from a young age to support his family, and witnessed the severe effect of War to the life of ordinary citizens. In most his literary writings author emphasizes family value, moral and social issues and preserving national identity. Utkir Hoshimov's literary style is known for its clarity, he wrote in a simple language which made it accessible for broader audience. His most acclaimed work is “Between two doors” is considered as the most influential in Uzbek Literature. This novel mainly emphasizes the war period and its reflection to peoples' life. Critisizing World War II period is the main pathos of the novel. Along with major issues like poverty and injustice he smoothly dive into insight world of ordinary people.

The writer enters into the soul of each character, narrating events from the perspective of a small child to the elderly people. Another themes he focused on his novel is family value, human dilemma between preserving traditional views and struggling with changing norms of the society.

Utkir Hoshimov also highlights the strong willpower of Uzbek nation in tough period. The author paints detailed portraits of people with diverse destiny, carefully depicting their work, life, behavior, and relationships. He emphasizes figures such as Husan Duma, Amma, Kamil Tabib, and Robiya, with deep frankness showing their kindness, truthfulness, loyalty. These characters show that humans should stay honest, righteous and wise in spite of what tragedy they face during their lives. Their strength is not only physical power but the inner light of their hearts and the purity of their soul.

He masterfully display the specifying qualities and the national spirit of the Uzbek people.

Conclusion. Either American Great Depression period or World War period in Uzbekistan undoubtedly impacted on the literary works of John Steinbeck and Utkir Hoshimov. Steinbeck, mainly focused on working-class struggle, highlighted justice, social inequality and exploitation in his novels and stories. Hoshimov, also meeting the difficulties of war and political issues, concentrated on moral integrity and the protection of national identity. Both authors illustrated social issues through the lives and struggles of ordinary people. Social circumstances served as a scenario for their works representing authentic historical events, real challenges and power of the community that overcome them.

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